

Tango of renewables in the triangle of uncertainty: A German case study

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ABSTRACT

Policymakers have strongly supported the widespread adoption of solar and wind energy as the two major pillars of the clean energy transition. Yet these energy sources are prone to weather and climate variability, which is often oversimplified in energy system models, resulting in a rather optimistic portrayal of these technologies as silver-bullet solutions. Bioenergy, with its inherent flexibility, can mitigate the negative impacts of renewable energy intermittency on a net-zero emissions energy system. As it takes two to tango, we analyze the interplay between variable renewable energy and dispatchable bioenergy, considering the past weather data using a risk-sensitive stochastic optimization model and future climate scenarios for Germany. Our outcomes propose that when solar and wind energy are abundant, the overall system cost is at a minimum, whereas during shortages, flexible bioenergy can support meeting electricity demand, albeit at a total system cost up to approximately 10% higher, depending on the condition. Moreover, our findings suggest that excessive risk sensitivity may drive greater dependence on dispatchable fossil energy, which poses a serious threat to achieving climate targets. Finally, we exhibit that under high availability of solar and wind energy, the investments in these technologies are more uniformly distributed across German federal states, whereas under lower availability, the northern and southern states are prioritized. While Germany serves as the case study, the methodology developed is universal and can be applied to other energy system optimization models with different geographical scopes, painting a more realistic picture of the future predicaments and solutions.

1. Introduction

To fulfill the climate targets and keep the 1.5 °C global warming limit within reach, further accelerated investments in the expansion of Variable Renewable Energy (VRE), such as solar and wind power, will be essential [1]. These renewable technologies are experiencing massive cost reductions and technological maturity, while fossil fuel extraction costs are continuously increasing [2]. In some places, even now, solar Photovoltaics (PV) has passed the grid parity point and has become the cheapest form of electricity generation [3]. Despite these advantages, VRE inherently depends on meteorological conditions (e.g., wind speed, irradiation, the air temperature, and humidity), making their integration and management complex. With the further de-fossilization of the energy system, the demand for renewable electricity will increase, as will the need for flexibility to compensate for its unpredictability. The recent blackout in the Iberian Peninsula, which impacted 55 million people, has been attributed to the high penetration of VREs, which contributed to widespread instability in the power system [4]. Battery storage systems are considered the leading solutions for maintaining grid stability [5]. Although battery

storage technologies can offer short-term flexibility in distributed systems and frequency regulation, they become less economical when selected for large power capability [6,7], which explains their modest contribution in future projections [8,9]. Furthermore, considering the techno-economic challenges, direct electrification will not be feasible for some energy-intensive processes [10]; thus, biomass might be a more affordable alternative for short- and mid-term storage, given its versatility as a relatively storable energy vector [11,12]. The effective management of such interconnected systems, characterized by contrasting objectives and competing solutions, requires the development of holistic decision-making tools.

As an indispensable part of energy supply chain management, Energy System Optimization Models (ESOMs) have been used since the 1970s to inform decision-makers and policymakers about strategic planning and future complexities of the energy system [13]. While the early attempts were to assess the impact of geopolitical conflicts on energy systems, these models are falling short in addressing new challenges, such as capturing the stochastic nature and investment risks associated with VRE [14]. To make matters worse, the lower spatiotemporal resolution of these models tends to overestimate the contribution

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from VRE (i.e., viewing VRE as a silver bullet), and underestimate CO₂ emissions [15] as well as total system cost [16].

Stochastic modeling emerged as a way of representing short-term variability in long-term energy models. Unlike deterministic models, where decisions are based on a single operational scenario with complete certainty, stochastic models define scenarios by considering the likelihood of different outcomes. Stochastic modeling improves representation of variable renewable energy in long-term energy models as it captures the need for back-up capacity and flexible solutions [17,18]. While stochastic modeling has predominantly been applied within the context of power systems [19,20], electricity represents just one facet of the broader energy landscape. To comprehensively understand the implications of VRE variability, it is essential to extend stochastic analysis to the entire energy system, encompassing various energy vectors and sectors, as the rapid aggravation of global climate change further exacerbates the uncertainty regarding risks [21]. All in all, this study aims to answer the following questions, which remain insufficiently addressed in the existing literature:

1. How can bioenergy (as an energy vector) help mitigate the intermittency of VREs?
2. How does risk-averse decision-making affect the achievement of future German climate targets?
3. What is the joint impact of climate change and weather variabilities on regional renewable energy investments in Germany?

To address these research questions, we investigate the interplay between VRE and dispatchable energy resources in the German energy system, including part of non-energy sectors, via a risk-sensitive stochastic model. The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows: (1) Using stochastic random variables, the uncertain power generation of intermittent renewable energy sources is integrated into the extended German bioenergy optimization model [22]. This allows to study the production of different biomass-requiring technologies until 2050 under different VRE availabilities in Germany. (2) Risk measures from portfolio optimization are introduced to account for risks in energy system models. (3) A scenario generation algorithm is proposed that considers both observations (past weather variability) and unknown dynamics of climate, using two climate scenarios, thereby combining stochastic modeling with sensitivity analysis to explore the solution space and empower a resilient energy system. Finally, the optimal technology deployment across German federal states is presented, incorporating variability at the NUTS-1 spatial resolution.

2. Literature review

To set this work in context, this section provides a critical review of pertinent literature on energy system modeling, tracing the conceptual and methodological development from its early days to the present. The rapid increase in crude oil prices following the oil crisis of the 1970s was a turning point in energy system modeling, as both industry and policymakers recognized the importance of long-term strategic energy planning [23]. Consequently, the International Energy Agency (IEA) was established in 1974, and the development of the first energy system model commenced in 1976 [24]. These earlier implementations, based on linear programming formulations [25], continue to be applied in various contexts to this day [26,27]. These first Energy System Models (ESMs) primarily focused on energy security and cost considerations, but over time, the emphasis shifted toward addressing security-of-supply problems [28]. Following the adoption of the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 [29], the development of models prioritizing Greenhouse Gas (GHG) reduction emerged [30], marking a transition in focus from economy, market behavior, technological issues, and environmental pollution to climate protection and sustainability [31]. By late 2015, increasing pressure from public authorities prompted a large majority of countries to strengthen their commitment to limiting the rise in

global mean temperature, leading to the Paris Agreement. To support this transition, the European Union (EU) passed the “Green Deal”, committing to reduce emissions by 50% relative to 1990 levels by 2030 [32]. In 2021, Germany updated its national climate law, moving the goal for climate neutrality to 2045 [33]. With the updated Renewable-Energies act 2023, the target of installed PV plants per year from 2026 onwards has been increased [34]. To strengthen the expansion of wind power, a binding land-use target for onshore wind was adopted in the Wind-on-Land act [35]. Moreover, the 2025 amendment of the Energy Industry Act introduced regulatory measures to mitigate temporary generation surpluses, enhance system flexibility, and improve congestion management in response to the increasing share of VRE [36].

Wijesinghe et al. [37] categorize disruptive events into four types: natural, human-caused intentional, socio-political, and economic, and emphasize that relying on a single objective, as in early models, often limits the ability to capture uncertainty and address heterogeneous stakeholder concerns. Gradually, research evolved by integrating renewable energy sources [23], emphasizing the need to account for VRE variability [31] and climate risks [38] at micro, meso, and macro decision scales [39]. This, consequently, drove demand for higher temporal and spatial resolution in ESMs, along with increased computational power.

Scientists employ multiple approaches to deal with the uncertainty of the system under investigation, such as scenario analysis, sensitivity analysis, and uncertainty analysis [40]. Depending on the research objectives, we may utilize scenario analysis to focus on a certain number of plausible futures or use sensitivity analysis to find the magnitude of system responses to variable inputs, or uncertainty analysis when the probabilistic information of these variable inputs is available. Near-optimal planning also emerges as a new approach; however, it can be viewed as a type of sensitivity analysis, not on input parameters but rather on the optimal solution(s) [41,42]. Although scientists have attempted to improve scenario analysis by assigning probability values based on past accuracy (i.e., hindcasting-based validation), these probabilities neither represent the true likelihood of the outcomes nor conform to principles of predictive reasoning [43]. Another approach is to employ rolling horizon instead of perfect foresight with full knowledge of the long-term scenarios. This way, the unknown information can be carried from the results of previous periods; however, this method also has its limitations [44].

Stochastic programming provides an effective method for capturing variability in energy modeling, accounting for the inherent uncertainty in most systems [45]. The method was introduced in the late 1950s [25] and is also applied in other research fields, such as health care [46], marketing [47], or production and supply planning [48]. McCollum et al. [49] underscore the importance of considering extreme energy futures in these scenarios. However, to eliminate the risk, stochastic optimization sometimes adheres to costly solutions. Chance constraints also emerged as an alternative to stochastic optimization, in which modelers reduce the costs of responding to the unexpected by ignoring extreme conditions, unlike stochastic optimization that plans in the face of uncertainty [50]. Risk measures, which were initially introduced in portfolio optimization within the financial industry, have proven to be efficient methods to maximize the profit of stakeholders, making them attractive for decision-makers [51]. Numerous risk measures exist in the literature—exemplified but not limited to Mean-Variance (MV), Value-at-Risk (VaR), and Conditional Value-at-Risk (CVaR). Each method has its own pros and cons; nonetheless, CVaR is often regarded as more plausible than VaR and MV methods [52]. Castro et al. [53] argue that MV assumes symmetric impacts of deviations, treating energy surplus and shortfall as equally significant, whereas energy shortfalls have more severe consequences. VaR is a favorable measure when the distribution of extreme events cannot be reliably estimated [54]. However, it exhibits undesirable mathematical properties, such as the lack of subadditivity and convexity [52]; consequently, CVaR is often

preferred [55]. Xuan et al. [56] integrate a risk measure (i.e., CVaR) in the objective function to balance the investment costs and operational risk in a simple energy system, and Zhao et al. [57] study risk aversion using CVaR in power systems under high-VRE penetration for China. Recently, the well-known PyPSA model (v1.0) embraced the CVaR measure, underlining the significance of accounting for tail risks in energy system models.¹

Uncertainty modeling can be applied to various aspects of energy systems, such as energy production and consumption. Nygaard et al. [58] study the optimal planning of risk-averse power systems surrounding the North Sea, considering the uncertainty of demand. In this study, however, we focus on the supply side, enabling us to differentiate between various VREs and assess their cascading impacts across the entire energy supply chain.

Talari et al. [59] classify various state-of-the-art approaches to stochastic modeling, including mathematical modeling, demand-side management, and the impact of different electricity market schemes. Stochastic modeling techniques encompass dependencies and independencies, multi-dimensional relationships, forecasts, and scenario analysis. The selection of an approach depends on the researcher's specific needs. For instance, Su et al. [60] use the point-forecast method to consider wind and solar in microgrid scheduling.

Additionally, alternative methods for integrating uncertainty into energy modeling have been explored. Perera et al. [61], for instance, use a machine-learning tool (i.e., Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs)) to quantify climate and human–system driven uncertainties in energy planning. Millinger et al. [62] employ near-optimal solutions to analyze the impact of the biomass shortage on the costs of the net-negative European energy system. Wijesinghe et al. [37] emphasize that providing a range of solutions (e.g., near-optimality or robust optimization) is key to boosting energy system resilience and adaptability. Moreover, Lombardi et al. [63] point out that providing alternative solutions can reduce the false sense of certainty. Gøtske et al. [64] linked PyPSA-Eur with an Integrated Assessment Model (IAM) across 100 scenario combinations of VRE shares in Europe to create a matrix.

In energy management systems, stochastic mixed-integer linear programs (SMILP) enable us to consider multiple stochastic scenarios [65]. In case of difficulty in specifying the probability distributions for the uncertain parameters (especially for extreme events), robust optimization uses uncertainty sets instead of stochastic scenarios [66,67]. The technique renders solutions that exhibit feasibility for all possible realizations of uncertainty within a range defined in the uncertainty set. Original box-type uncertainty sets were only able to accommodate the most conservative uncertainty manifestations; nowadays various types of uncertainty sets, such as polyhedral or ellipsoidal, can be found in literature [68]. For a day-ahead power market, Jiang et al. [69] developed a robust optimization model to accommodate wind output uncertainty and applied their model to a six-bus system. Moret et al. [70] compare a robust optimization framework to a deterministic approach to analyze overcapacity in European power systems. Their work shows that considering uncertainties in the long-term planning process can reduce the risk of generating overcapacity in national power systems. Adaptive Robust Optimization (ARO) improves the original static robust optimization by incorporating multiple stages of decision into the algorithm [71]. Riepin et al. [72] apply an ARO to invest long-term uncertainties in natural gas models. A detailed review is provided by Roald et al. [73]. García-Cerezo et al. [74] compare stochastic optimization with robust optimization and show that robust optimization often invests more in VREs to hedge against customers who are not willing to pay high marginal costs for conventional generation.

De Marco et al. [75] categorize 60 future climate scenarios into five representative ones and apply a stochastic optimization model to solve them at the European scale with national-level resolution. The

authors show that resilient planning increases the capacities of biomass boiler plants. Using PyPSA-Eur, Gøtske et al. [76] perform a sensitivity analysis to understand the reliability of the European energy system concerning weather variability using 62 weather years. The authors optimized the European model based on each of the 62 weather years as the design year, then fixed the optimal capacities under the design year and introduced the other 61 weather years (operational years) to find the impact on the total system costs. They conclude that the total system costs can vary by $\pm 10\%$. As mentioned by the authors, one valid criticism of this approach is to analyze solely one year and not a longer time horizon, and trends caused by the combination of weather years. In this current study, a combination of weather years until 2050 is introduced into the developed model to analyze trends.

Seljom and Tomasgard [77] analyze the uncertainty in wind power generation in Denmark using a novel stochastic approach within the TIMES model for the Danish heat and electricity sector. The employed scenarios are based on wind power production data from 2006 to 2011, and the results reveal a reduction in total system costs and an increase in biomass consumption. Seljom et al. [17] evaluate different scenario generation methods using the TIMES model of the Norwegian energy system. Based on hourly-derived PV- and wind generation data, the scenarios are generated by using different clustering algorithms and sampling techniques. The authors show that the model runtime is highly dependent on the number of scenarios used. Ringkjøb et al. [78] apply the TIMES model for the European power and district heating sector to compare deterministic and stochastic approaches across various temporal resolutions. Their results demonstrate that a stochastic approach with a coarser temporal resolution outperforms a deterministic model with finer resolution, offering improved results and reduced computational time. Based on these findings, they recommend the use of a stochastic long-term Energy System Optimization Model (ESOM) with sector coupling. Dominguez et al. [79] study the European power system for 2050 by solving a two-stage stochastic programming problem. In contrast to optimization problems solved under perfect foresight, models using the rolling horizon approach divide the problem into intervals, solving each successively while passing the time-dependent variables to the next interval. In the first step, the day-ahead energy and reserve markets are modeled, followed by real-time operations in the second step. The results indicate that most new generating capacity will be deployed after 2030, with a notable increase in installed biomass capacity. Likewise, both Dominguez et al. [79] and Seljom et al. [17] generate equiprobable scenarios from historical data.

The examined studies highlight the differences in existing stochastic ESOMs, particularly in their random variable selection, risk analysis, scenario generation methods, and the regional and temporal scopes they address; however, 2050 serves as a critical target year. A review of the literature indicates that the introduction of stochastic programming results in an increased biomass usage for energy generation [77,79]. Nevertheless, existing models often fail to capture the versatile and flexible usage options of biomass. The literature review highlights a general lack of detail in biomass representation: In some cases, biomass is entirely omitted [70], while in others, biomass is determined exogenously without distinguishing between different crop types or technologies [77,78]. While the interplay of hydropower and VRE has been studied using the stochastic optimization model FanSi [80], the necessity for an extensive stochastic optimization model with detailed information on biomass, and sector-coupling that accounts for risk is identified [81]. Table 1 presents a structured comparison across multiple criteria of the current work with selected relevant studies discussed in this section. The studies are ordered chronologically by publication year and are compared in six categories: use of scenarios, sensitivity analysis, type stochastic modeling, risk analysis, investigated sector, and applied case study.

To address this gap in the literature, this paper presents the implementation of stochastic programming for VRE in the extended Bioenergy Optimization model (BENOPTex). BENOPTex includes detailed

¹ See <https://docs.pypsa.org/latest/release-notes/>

Table 1

Comparing the most-related studies in the literature based on six categories. ✓ shows that the study in the row covers the dimension in the column. R appears exclusively in the stochastic column, indicating the use of robust optimization.

	Year	Scenario	Sensitivity	Stochastic	Risk	Sector	Case study
Jiang et al. [69]	2011	✓				Power	..
Pina et al. [26]	2011	✓				Power	Azores
Zeng and Zhao [71]	2013		✓			Power	..
Gracceva and Zeniewski [27]	2013	✓	✓			Energy	Global
Su et al. [60]	2013	✓		✓		Microgrids	..
Seljom and Tomasgard [77]	2015	✓		✓		Power	Denmark
Lappas and Gounaris [68]	2018			R		Energy and Non-energy	..
Bahramara and Golpîra [66]	2018	✓	✓	✓	✓	Microgrids	..
Moret et al. [70]	2020			R		Power	Europe
Ringkjøb et al. [78]	2020	✓		✓		Power and District heat	Europe
Dominguez et al. [79]	2020	✓		✓		Power	Europe
Kaisermayer et al. [65]	2021	✓		✓		Energy management	..
Seljom et al. [17]	2021	✓	✓	✓		Energy	Norway
Xuan et al. [56]	2021	✓		✓	✓	Energy	..
Perera et al. [61]	2022	✓		✓		Energy and Non-energy	Switzerland
Riepin et al. [72]	2022	✓	✓	R		Gas-market	Europe
Gøtske et al. [76]	2024	✓	✓	✓		Energy	Europe
Chen et al. [50]	2024		✓	✓	✓	Power	Rwanda
Nygaard et al. [58]	2025		✓	✓	✓	Power	North Sea
Millinger et al. [62]	2025	✓	✓			Energy	Europe
Gøtske et al. [64]	2025	✓	✓			Energy and Non-energy	Europe
De Marco et al. [75]	2025	✓		✓		Energy	Europe
This study	2026	✓	✓	✓	✓	Energy and Non-energy	Germany (NUTS-1)

conversion pathways to provide insights into the transition from fossil energy sources to bioenergy, and it integrates various energy-related and non-energy-related sectors (see Fig. G.13). The interplay between VRE and bioenergy is endogenously taken into account, considering past weather variabilities, climate scenarios, and risk sensitivity. This paper analyzes two climate scenarios (RCP2.6 and RCP6.0)² and conducts an extensive sensitivity analysis (including risk-sensitivity) on various parameters of the stochastic model, as detailed in the results section. Furthermore, the proposed model encompasses both energy and selected non-energy sectors, including Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) [83] and bioeconomy-related chemical industries [84], with a regional resolution at the federal state level (i.e., NUTS-1) in Germany, reflecting the spatial dependence of VRE technologies.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section 3, we explain how the raw data is retrieved, organized, and grouped into principal categories. Then, the required changes to convert the deterministic optimization model into a risk-sensitive stochastic optimization model are described. Section 4 presents results for various scenarios, which will be followed by a discussion in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes.

3. Methods

3.1. Retrieving historic data

To capture variability, scenarios are generated using 40 years of historical weather data (i.e., $|H| = 40$). Capacity Factor (CF)³ for wind (onshore and offshore) and solar PV are collected from Renewables.Ninja [85,86]. These hourly CFs, describing the ratio of actual energy generation to the potential energy generation during the given

² Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) are extracted from the LPJmL model [82] and affect the regional yields of energy crops in the BENOPTex model [81].

³ Capacity factor is the ratio of actual power produced over a given period of time to the maximum theoretical power over the same period.

time period, are the outcomes of simulations based on past weather information from 1980 until 2019 on a national scale for all European countries. Data entries from the 29th of February are eliminated from the dataset to align the leap years with normal years.

3.2. Clustering capacity factors

The obtained CFs for the last forty years were analyzed using different clustering algorithms, among which k-means, k-medoids, and hierarchical clustering performed as expected. Three clusters – low, med, and high CF – have been defined. Depending on whether wind or sun is considered, the assessment of low or high performance weather year differs.

For each type of VRE, k-means and k-medoids clusters were initialized using historically known good and bad weather years, whereas hierarchical clustering, which does not rely on centroids, was labeled post hoc according to the mean value of each cluster. The clusters retained the same label under median-based mapping. Cluster sizes differ according to technology, clustering algorithm and type of VRE. Fig. 1 shows the average and standard deviation of VREs of different clusters when these algorithms are used. Among the evaluated clustering methods, hierarchical clustering produced the most compact and least dispersed clusters, as indicated by the smallest interquartile ranges and whisker lengths in the resulting box plots. Thus, after reviewing the outcomes of various clustering algorithms, we employ hierarchical clustering, as it provides more distinct clusters with greater average spacing and generally lower standard deviation. For example, hierarchical clustering yields a partitioning of the onshore wind data into mutually exclusive, non-overlapping clusters.

3.3. Generating scenarios

This study aims to assess the impact of weather variability and bioenergy on the German energy system using historical data. As the focus is not forecasting future conditions, the narrative is of secondary importance. Instead, we explore the feasible solution space through sensitivity analysis in three dimensions: low-VRE, mid-VRE, and high-VRE. Depending on the respective created cluster (low-VRE, mid-VRE,

Fig. 1. (a)–(c) Comparison of the three tested clustering algorithms on the capacity factor using box plots. The lower box limit represents the 25th percentile, the upper box limit the 75th percentile, and the line inside the box the median for each clustering algorithm.

Fig. 2. All feasible combinations of scenarios.

high-VRE) in Section 3.2, weather years are sorted to the dimensions for each technology (i.e., solar, wind onshore and wind offshore). Therefore, low-VRE means all VREs are in their worse availabilities. Since the total probability must sum to 100%, all feasible mixture combinations of these scenarios lie on the blue facet of Fig. 2(a). Point E on the facet represents the current probabilities of low-VRE, mid-VRE, and high-VRE, derived from 40 years of historical data; however, rather than focusing solely on this single point within the solution space, we present the full spectrum, as future climate conditions may alter the frequency of occurrence of these categories. For example, some studies show wind energy potential may decline in the future under climate change [87]; therefore, the rays from E toward low-VRE are especially important.

At each point on the facet, the combination of these three clusters is randomly distributed, resulting in multiple potential solutions. By randomly distributing these aspects into future years, we can analyze the impact on trends. But this requires numerous replications for each combination to eliminate modeling artifacts. For instance, at point A, in 50% of the years between 2020 and 2050, a scenario is randomly selected from the high-VRE category, and in the remaining years from the low-VRE category; however, the distribution of these scenarios over the planning horizon is randomized. The reported numbers in Section 4 are aggregated from 10,000 replications conducted at discrete points on the feasible space as shown in Fig. 2(b). To accelerate the execution time, each discrete point on the facet is processed by a parallel solver.

3.4. Incorporating intermittency in the risk-neutral model

To incorporate VRE, we expand the BENOPTex model [22], a deterministic perfect foresight ESOM, considering the latest policies in place.⁴ Regional hourly electricity demand is harmonized through the coupling of REMix and BENOPTex models [89]. Historical CFs are collected and categorized in MATLAB and passed down to the optimization model, which is implemented in GAMS to be incorporated as stochastic variables. Doing so, the resulting optimization model considers both deterministic variables (e.g., energy produced by dispatchable technologies) and stochastic variables (e.g., power produced by solar PVs and wind turbines).

For modeling the intermittency of wind and solar, a stochastic decision variable is introduced for each intermittent VRE in every time slice j of each year $t \in T$ from 2020 until 2050. In the deterministic model, Eq. (1) limits the amount of electricity (E^{el}) that can be produced (in PJ) from the dispatchable technology i at time slice j of year t in region r , where $\beta_j = (8760 \cdot 0.0036 / J^{max})$ is a coefficient that converts GWh to PJ considering the maximum number of time slices ($J^{max} = |J|$), k_{ti} is the deployed capacity in GW, and C_{tir} specifies the availability of technology i at year t in region r . C_{tir} excludes the maintenance time

⁴ For instance, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) is considered according to the base scenario of Aliabadi et al. [88].

when power plants cannot produce electricity.

$$E_{tjir}^{el} \leq \beta_j k_{ti} C_{tir} \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{CONvel}}, j \in J, r \in R \quad (1)$$

Unlike dispatchable technologies, the capacity factors of intermittent renewable technologies (\tilde{C}_{tir}) are random stochastic variables that depend on weather conditions. Alternatively, as formulated in Eq. (2), the owners of these facilities can purchase electricity (\tilde{P}_{tjir}) from local electricity markets to meet the required optimal amount.⁵ Since the optimal purchase is dependent on the capacity factor, its value is also a function of the stochastic variable. To simplify, we assume that fluctuations between time slices in electricity generation can be adjusted with \tilde{P}_{tjir} ; however, the optimal deployed capacities (k_{ti}^*) are determined in a perfect foresight intertemporal optimization minimizing total system costs. Hence, short-term variability is handled operationally but remains fully internalized in long-term investment decisions. This assumption underlines the fact that installed capacities represent strategic decisions and should not be equally affected by short-term variabilities. Furthermore, we assume that \tilde{P}_{tjir} and \tilde{C}_{tir} are independent random variables as they are governed by different systems and constraints (see Appendix C). Finally, excess electricity production is assumed to be wasted. In this study, we exclude the utility-scale Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) as these technologies are currently difficult to recommend, considering their costs [9].

$$E_{tjir}^{el} \leq \beta_j k_{ti} \tilde{C}_{tir} + \tilde{P}_{tjir} \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j,i} \tilde{P}_{tjir} \leq \hat{P}_{ir} \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, r \in R \quad (3)$$

Due to strict data protection regulations [90], spatially and temporally detailed power production data are not publicly available in Germany; thus, scientists must explore alternative methods to fill this data gap. In this study, the national CFs are downscaled to the federal state level using the outcomes of a physics-aware simulation model (ReSTEP) based on weather data in 2020 [91], quantifying region-specific differences in wind speed and solar irradiance arising from Germany's geographical setting [92]. Eq. (3) sets an upper bound (\hat{P}_{ir}) for the purchased electricity from local markets. Different realizations of \tilde{C}_{tir} in Eq. (2) can be formulated using scenarios. Each scenario ($s \in \Omega$) has a probability of occurrence ($p^s \in [0, 1]$). Therefore, Eq. (2) can be formulated as

$$E_{tjir}^{el} \leq \beta_j k_{ti} C_{tir}^s + P_{tjir}^s \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R, s \in \Omega \quad (4)$$

where the included surplus variable, P_{tjir}^s , has a real-world meaning, facilitating finding the penalty for that variable in the objective function. In Eq. (4), P_{tjir}^s describes the additional electricity that has to be purchased by VRE technology i at time slice j of year t in region r under the realized scenario s , in order to compensate the deviation from the optimal allocation of the independent system operator. Since the additional electricity has to be purchased from external sources, one can associate a cost to it in the objective function, penalizing its occurrence.

The objective is to minimize the total system cost over the entire planning horizon, $\min \sum_t (z_t)$, for different energy carriers, including electricity. As shown in Eq. (6), the annual system costs (z_t) in the objective function consists of deterministic and stochastic terms. The deterministic term includes, but is not limited to, the production costs, investment costs of dispatchable technologies, and feedstock costs. The stochastic part, on the other hand, minimizes the expected (average) cost of purchasing additional electricity to satisfy the demand depending on the current power price (p_{ti}^{el}). It is assumed that any excess electricity production is wasted as it will not be traded in the market.

⁵ This optimal amount may result from market clearing in the day-ahead market, and any deviations should be balanced through the balancing market.

Interested readers may refer to Appendix G for more information on the objective function and other power-related constraints.

$$z_t = \underbrace{\sum_i (z_{ti})}_{\text{deterministic term}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{ijs} (p_{ti}^{el} \cdot P_{tjir}^s) \right]}_{\text{stochastic term}} \quad , \forall t \in T \quad (5)$$

$$= \sum_i z_{ti} + \sum_{ijs} (p_{ti}^{el} \cdot \mathbb{E} [P_{tjir}^s]) \quad , \forall t \in T \quad (6)$$

Increasing the number of scenarios enhances result accuracy but also extends computation time. For example, a model with a 12-hour resolution and 100 replications can take up to 12 days to complete. Therefore, we leverage the model structure to accelerate computation. Please note that maintaining a linear model structure is another requirement for this study, as linear models remain tractable and solvable even at large scales. Linear programming models are widely employed in the context of energy systems due to their large scale [93], which enhances the applicability of this approach to other modeling contexts. As shown in Eq. (6), the only required parameter is the expected value of purchased electricity. By taking the expected value on both sides of Eq. (2), and noting that all other decision variables and parameters are deterministic or constant, we replace $\mathbb{E} [\tilde{C}_{tir}]$ with the average value and therefore

$$\mathbb{E} [E_{tjir}^{el}] \leq \mathbb{E} [\beta_j k_{ti} \tilde{C}_{tir} + \tilde{P}_{tjir}] \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbb{E} [\tilde{P}_{tjir}] \geq E_{tjir}^{el} - \beta_j k_{ti} \mathbb{E} [\tilde{C}_{tir}] \quad , \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R. \quad (8)$$

Since the objective function is to minimize the cost, the minimum $\mathbb{E} [\tilde{P}_{tjir}]$ value in Eq. (8) is $E_{tjir}^{el} - \beta_j k_{ti} \mathbb{E} [\tilde{C}_{tir}]$. To use this property in a general form, we employ Algorithm 1, in which a roulette wheel technique is employed to assign scenarios to different years, given the probabilities of each category. To reduce the modeling artifacts, thousands of replications are generated for each setting. Finally, interested readers are referred to Appendix F for a proof of the optimality of the modified model with respect to the original model.

3.5. Incorporating intermittency in the risk-sensitive model

While we use the expected value of the capacity factor in Section 3, alternative risk measures such as VaR and CVaR can also be applied to incorporate risk sensitivity. VaR and CVaR quantify potential investment losses under normal market conditions within a given time frame, providing a more comprehensive assessment of risk [54]. According to the definition, if $X \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma^2)$ then $VaR_\alpha(X) = \mu + Z_\alpha \cdot \sigma$ where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is the confidence interval and $Z_\alpha = 2.33$ for $\alpha = 99\%$ and 1.645 for $\alpha = 95\%$, corresponding to the quantile function of the standard normal distribution $\Psi^{-1}(\alpha)$. On the other hand, $CVaR_\alpha(X) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \int_0^\alpha VaR_\zeta(X) d\zeta$. CVaR is employed when the random variable X is fat-tailed. Alexander and Baptista [94] show that for a given confidence level, a CVaR constraint is tighter than a VaR constraint when the bounds coincide.

To incorporate VaR, we can change z_t in the objective function as

$$z_t = \sum_i (z_{ti}) + \overbrace{\lambda VaR_\alpha \left(\sum_{ijs} (p_{ti}^{el} \cdot P_{tjir}^s) \right)}^{\text{risk measure}} \quad , \forall t \in T \quad (9)$$

$$= \sum_i (z_{ti}) + \lambda \left(\sum_{ijs} (p_{ti}^{el} \cdot VaR_\alpha(P_{tjir}^s)) \right) \quad , \forall t \in T \quad (10)$$

$$= \sum_i (z_{ti}) + \lambda \sum_{ijs} \left(p_{ti}^{el} \cdot \left(\mathbb{E}[P_{tjir}^s] + Z_\alpha \cdot \sigma[P_{tjir}^s] \right) \right) \quad , \forall t \in T \quad (11)$$

where λ is a trade-off parameter between minimizing cost or VaR. In some other studies, λ is split into two terms λ and $1 - \lambda$ to distinguish between the risk-neutral and risk-sensitive model [58]. Eq. (10) exploits the positive homogeneity and translation invariance properties of VaR, which says $VaR_\alpha(a + b \cdot X) = a + b \cdot VaR_\alpha(X)$ for $a \in \mathcal{R}$ and $b > 0$ [95]. In this study, we assume that P_{tjir}^s follows a normal distribution to simplify

the derivation of Eq. (11); however, please note that the validity of this normality assumption is case-specific (see Appendix D). For $\alpha = 50\%$ and $\lambda = 1$, Eq. (11) is similar to Eq. (6). To compute Eq. (11), the standard deviation of purchased power is required (i.e., $\sigma[P_{tjir}^s]$). In general, we know that the variance of any random variable is a non-negative value; therefore, in inequality (12), $\sigma^2[\beta_j k_{ii} \tilde{C}_{tjir} + \tilde{P}_{tjir}] \geq 0$. Assuming that the other terms are either coefficient or independent decision variables from \tilde{P}_{tjir} ,⁶ we can have the standard deviation as

$$\sigma^2[\beta_j k_{ii} \tilde{C}_{tjir} + \tilde{P}_{tjir}] \geq 0, \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma^2[\tilde{P}_{tjir}] \geq (-\beta_j k_{ii})^2 \sigma^2[\tilde{C}_{tjir}], \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\sigma^2[\tilde{P}_{tjir}]} &\geq \sqrt{(\beta_j^2 k_{ii}^2) \sigma^2[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]} && \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R \\ \sigma[\tilde{P}_{tjir}] &\geq (\beta_j k_{ii}) \sigma[\tilde{C}_{tjir}] && \forall i \in I^{\text{VRE}}, j \in J, r \in R. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

To derive Eq. (14), we assume $\text{cov}(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \approx 0$, which is discussed in Appendix C. Moreover, the bound on the covariance is provided in Appendix C.1. Combining Eqs. (11) and (14), we obtain the following objective function that accounts for the VaR.

$$\min \sum_t z_t = \sum_t \left(\sum_i (z_{ii}) + \lambda \sum_{ijs} \left(p_{ii}^{el} \cdot \left(\mathbb{E}[P_{tjir}^s] + Z_\alpha \cdot (\beta_j k_{ii}) \cdot \sigma[\tilde{C}_{tjir}] \right) \right) \right) \quad (15)$$

In addition to the VaR, we can calculate the CVaR. Acerbi [96] showed that CVaR is equivalent to expected shortfall (ES) under the assumption that the probability distribution function is continuous. In this work, we consider the cost function as continuous. As specified above, $VaR_\alpha(X) = \mu + Z_\alpha \cdot \sigma$, then $CVaR_\alpha(X) = \mu + \frac{\Phi(Z_\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \cdot \sigma$, where $\Phi(Z_\alpha)$ corresponds to the probability density function of the standard normal distribution evaluated at Z_α . Following the previous assumptions, the following objective function accounts for CVaR instead of VaR.

$$\min \sum_t z_t = \sum_t \left(\sum_i (z_{ii}) + \lambda \sum_{ijs} \left(p_{ii}^{el} \cdot \left(\mathbb{E}[P_{tjir}^s] + \frac{\Phi(Z_\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \cdot (\beta_j k_{ii}) \cdot \sigma[\tilde{C}_{tjir}] \right) \right) \right) \quad (16)$$

4. Results

For 10K replications (x^{max}), we run Algorithm 1 with a resolution of 25% and 730 time slices. Moreover, we set $\lambda = 1$, since both the risk-neutral and risk-sensitive cases share the same cost unit (i.e., million euros). Solving the model under these conditions requires more than 21 h on a workstation equipped with 72 Intel Xeon E-78867 processors (2.4 GHz) and 6 TB of RAM. For each setting on the ternary plot, the GAMS optimizer is configured to allocate six threads to the CPLEX solvers: One thread each for the primal and dual simplex algorithms, and four threads for the interior point method. The optimization models corresponding to these settings are generated and executed in parallel.

As shown in Fig. 3, the mix of VREs in 2050 depends on the regional availability of these technologies. The composition of VREs is shown as pie charts within each state in the first row, and the total capacity is represented by the state's shading: Darker shades indicate higher VRE penetration. Also, the transmission lines are depicted between states. Under the high-VRE scenario, the model invests in VREs more uniformly across states, primarily due to the widespread availability of

⁶ This is an important requirement, assuming that any deviation from optimal production between time slices ($j \in J$) can be addressed through external purchases rather than by altering the optimal deployed capacity in year t .

Algorithm 1 Scenario generation algorithm

Require: $\lambda \geq 0$, $\alpha \geq 50\%$, and x^{max} is the maximum number of replications

Require: $Pr(S_c) \geq 0$ such that $\sum_c Pr(S_c) = 1$

- 1: $x \leftarrow 0$
- 2: **while** $x \leq x^{\text{max}}$ **do**
- 3: $x \leftarrow x + 1$ ▷ Generate multiple replications
- 4: $t \leftarrow 0$
- 5: **while** $t \leq |T|$ **do**
- 6: $t \leftarrow t + 1$
- 7: $r \sim U(0, 1)$ ▷ Generate a random number between 0 and 1
- 8: **if** $r \in [0, Pr(S_1)]$ **then**
- 9: $s_t^x \in S_{c_1}$ ▷ Choose a scenario randomly from S_{c_1}
- 10: **else if** $r \in (Pr(S_{c_1}), Pr(S_{c_1}) + Pr(S_{c_2}))$ **then**
- 11: $s_t^x \in S_{c_2}$ ▷ Choose a scenario randomly from S_{c_2}
- 12: **else**
- 13: $s_t^x \in S_{c_3}$ ▷ Choose a scenario randomly from S_{c_3}
- 14: **end if**
- 15: **end while**
- 16: **end while**
- 17: Calculate $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]$ and $\sigma[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]$
- 18: Optimize BENOPTex with Eqs. (6), (15), or (16) for the risk-neutral or the risk-sensitive models, respectively.

solar energy. In contrast, under the low-VRE scenario, northern states focus more on wind energy and southern states prioritize solar energy, while states located in the central region invest less overall compared to those in the north or south. This results in Bavaria in a capacity multiple times higher than the average of all states under low-VRE scenario in comparison to high-VRE scenario, reflecting patterns similar to the current situation.⁷ This outcome is in accordance with Brandes et al. [97]. Another important observation is that although \tilde{P}_{tjir} does not directly alter k_{ii} in year t in Eq. (2), it guides the optimal deployment of VREs indirectly through the purchased power variable, thereby generating contrasting projections for future VRE capacities under low- and high-VRE scenarios. The second row in Fig. 3 illustrates the cultivation of energy crops across German states under high- and low-VRE scenarios. Niedersachsen (Lower Saxony) stands out with particularly high biomass production, supported by its extensive wetlands that are well-suited for paludiculture. We also observe regional shifts in the types of energy crops, driven by the availability of electricity, since bioenergy relies on specific forms of biomass to meet demand. In periods of lower electricity generation from solar and wind, miscanthus becomes more prevalent, particularly in the western and southern states, where it helps meet heat sector demand due to the lower availability of heat pumps [98].

Fig. 4 displays the response of the German energy system to various levels of risk aversion and risk measures using ternary graphs. Each axis shows how often (the probability) a scenario from each category is picked over the years, and the diagonal vertices symbolize different combinations of scenarios over the years, as illustrated in Fig. 2(a). In each triangular plot, the results are presented using a color-coded scheme with red corresponds to high values and blue indicating low values. The outcomes are normalized relative to the maximum value across all combinations. The first column displays the system cost, while the second and third columns show the total energy produced from 2020 to 2050 by VRE and bioenergy, respectively. The key takeaway is that bioenergy and VRE complement each other: When power production from VRE is low, bioenergy compensates, albeit at a higher cost. This outcome is consistent with findings from other

⁷ <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/dossiers/onshore-wind-power-germany>

Fig. 3. First row: A risk-sensitive (i.e., VaR with $\alpha = 99\%$) mixture of VREs (installed capacities in GW) in different German states in 2050 when $\sum_r \hat{P}_{ir} = 70$ PJ. The darker-shaded states represent higher deployment of VREs. Second row: The cultivation of energy crops in various German states in 2050 under low-VRE and high-VRE scenarios in PJ. Transmission lines between these states are illustrated on the plots in the first row.

studies that highlight the value of bioenergy in providing flexibility to energy systems with high shares of VRE [99,100]. To compete with VREs, bioenergy must overcome many institutional and techno-economic barriers [101]. The higher costs result from higher prices of BECCS technologies, which are used more under the low-VRE scenario. Higher costs are partly related to higher investment costs and higher opex costs for BECCS.

As the model's risk-aversion increases from risk neutral ($\alpha = 50\%$) to VaR with $\alpha = 95\%$, the blue sections of the cost plot turn yellowish. This cost increase can be associated with the greater tendency of the model to invest in dispatchable power (e.g., bioenergy) when the intermittency of VREs is high. This trend continues when α increases to 99%, as the VaR model becomes more sensitive to risk and invests in dispatchable technologies, such as bioenergy and fossil fuels, and removes additional CO₂ emissions using Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS). For the risk-sensitive model with CVaR at $\alpha = 95\%$, the model acts more risk-averse than VaR at higher α values ($\alpha = 99\%$). This can be due to the fat-tailed cost distribution. Increasing α to

99% while employing CVaR increases costs further, and the maximum amount of VRE will only be employed when the variability of VREs is low at 100% high-VRE scenarios. Across all scenario combinations, the risk-averse strategy (CVaR, $\alpha = 99\%$) consistently results in higher costs compared to the risk-neutral approach. Specifically, under the 100% high-VRE scenario, the risk-averse model leads to a cost increase of approximately 14% relative to the risk-neutral setting. We can also witness that a second reddish region appears under CVaR with $\alpha = 99\%$ at the center of the cost graph. This is the artifact of extreme conditions where the optimization model opposes technologies with even minor variabilities, leading to flattening the cost function.⁸

The risk-averse behavior is clearly illustrated in Fig. 5, where increasing α from 50% to 99% has led to a greater reliance on fossil fuels

⁸ The gap between the minimum and the maximum costs is reduced from ~5.4% under the risk-neutrality to ~1.2% under extreme risk-sensitivity (i.e., CVaR with $\alpha = 99\%$).

Fig. 4. German energy system response to various risk aversion level when $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr} = 100$. The risk-neutral and risk-sensitive ($\lambda = 1$ and $\alpha = 50\%$ for the first row and $\alpha = 95\%$ for the second row, and $\alpha = 99\%$ for the third row) energy system under various mixtures of scenarios. The last two rows represent the risk-sensitive model using the CVaR when $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr} = 100$ and $\alpha = 95\%$, and $\alpha = 99\%$ in the last row. Each point is replicated 10,000 times with the temporal resolution of 730 time slices per year.

and dispatchable renewables, while reducing the share of VREs. This outcome indicates that with higher risk sensitivity, BECCS emerges as an attractive option (especially in low-VRE settings) for both generating dispatchable energy and mitigating CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels. This is similar to the case of no carbon price in Nygaard et al. [58], in which moving away from the risk-neutral perspective to the risk-averse led to more investments in coal-fired power plants. However,

we should also note that in Nygaard et al. [58] only electricity demand was uncertain; thus, in a scenario with CO₂ price, more investments in solar and wind energy were suggested. Combining the insights from these papers suggests that modeling uncertainty should be taken into account in the supply and demand for energy.

According to Fig. 6, the maximum emissions are at extreme low-VRE corners and minimum emissions are at the high-VRE corners.

Fig. 5. The amount of energy produced from 2020 until 2050 between extreme settings under risk-neutral and risk-averse (VaR and CVaR) cases.

Comparing the cost-optimal solutions under risk-neutral and risk-averse cases reveals that total emissions increase with higher risk sensitivity, primarily due to greater reliance on dispatchable fossil resources. However, the deployment of BECCS helps narrow this gap—under the risk-averse case, the minimum emissions are only about 2.5% lower than the maximum. Finally, the total emissions in the risk-neutral case (see Fig. 6(a)) exhibit a smoother gradient compared to the risk-sensitive case, reflecting the less complex substitution of technologies. This suggests that under risk-sensitive decision-making, the notion of a single ‘silver bullet’ solution becomes less relevant. In comparison, Fig. 6(c) shows the total emissions when CVaR is employed. The emissions are the highest compared to all analyzed cases. This is in accordance with the high reliance on dispatchable fossil fuels.

To consider international collaboration, we incorporate the carbon credit option into our model, which prevents infeasibility in years when climate targets cannot be achieved domestically. Needless to say, the availability and unit purchase cost of these credits are uncertain; however, we assume that some European and non-European countries may exceed their emission reduction targets and be willing to sell their surplus removals as credits to countries that fail to meet their climate goals, albeit at higher unit costs. Fig. 6(d) shows the cost for carbon credits that are bought externally yearly to compensate for emissions exceeding the yearly decreasing carbon budget as defined in the German climate law [33]. Emissions are quantified for all energy-related sectors, while emissions from non-energy sectors are incorporated exogenously (see Appendix G.4). Negative emissions from carbon removal technologies are credited against gross emissions. Emissions from imported energy carriers and imported biomass that are used for domestic energy production are fully accounted for. However, emissions associated with electricity through the balancing market are not attributed to the national carbon budget, in line with territorial accounting. Again, low availability of VRE results in higher costs due to the use of fossil energy and paying the penalty to purchase carbon credits from other countries to reach climate targets. We also observe that in most settings, payments range between 2.2 and 3.2 $\times 10^5$ million euros, as paying 10% above the CO₂ price for purchasing these credits remains economically viable compared to alternative options. As the decision-maker becomes increasingly risk-averse, the reliance on purchasing carbon credits to offset emissions increases accordingly. Unfortunately, the current trends affirm that paying such penalties is becoming more relevant [102]. For the domestic CO₂ price, a price development until 250 €/tCO₂ in 2050 is used and although we assume external credits cost 10% more than the domestic CO₂ price, variations in this value could change the exact numbers in this figure; however, the main message will stay valid.

The influence of risk aversion on GHG emissions indicates that risk sensitivity should be well-tuned to achieve lower emissions while creating a more resilient energy system. The resilience of the energy system and supply security are the core topics in the EU, especially after the Russo-Ukraine war, leading to REPowerEU [103]. Nonetheless, REPowerEU mainly concentrates on strategic resilience rather than operational risks, which is gradually showing its impact on European energy systems [4].

5. Discussion

5.1. Interplay of battery storage and biomass

In this work, BESS was not explicitly implemented; however, as shown in Fig. G.16, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis was performed on external purchased power (\hat{P}_{tr}), which can originate from distributed systems. Assuming that the utility-scale BESS in Germany is expected to remain below one PJ by 2050 [8], our results can be considered relatively relaxed, and therefore, it is reasonable to assume that \hat{P}_{tr} includes the available power in distributed BESS, such as through Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G). Thus, the derived conclusions remain valid unless the techno-economic parameters of novel storage technologies change substantially.

Due to its additional benefits, such as carbon removal and dispatchability, bioenergy plays an increasingly important role in high risk-sensitive cases, especially under low-VRE scenarios in which further deployment of BECCS is required to offset emissions from natural gas-fired power plants. Moreover, BESS can mitigate merely short-term variability, while bioenergy offers mid-term seasonal flexibility [104]. Despite these benefits, a greater reliance on bioenergy also leads to higher costs; however, it is still more cost-effective than other alternatives (such as Power-to-X and BESS) in hard-to-abate sectors [105]. Fig. 7 shows heat and transport sectors as the most prominent users of biomass in the German energy sector. Nonetheless, increasing risk sensitivity can redirect part of the utilized biomass from the heat to the power sector.

5.2. Envisaged VRE targets

A comparison of the 2050 capacity mix under low- and high-VRE scenarios in the risk-neutral setting (the first row in Fig. 8) reveals that dispatchable sources contribute marginally compared to VREs; however, there remains competition between solar energy and dispatchable technologies. Under the high-VRE scenario, widespread solar PV deployment and high CFs diminish the need for fossil fuels

Fig. 6. (a)–(c) The total emissions in KtCO₂-eq, and (d)–(f) the total purchased credit from other countries (in million €) over the planning horizon for the risk-neutral and the risk-averse cases.

Fig. 7. Allocation of biomass to various sectors under different levels of risk-sensitivity at high availability of VRE.

and bioenergy. Conversely, in the low-VRE scenario, the model reduces solar PV investment and compensates with increased reliance on bioenergy and gas turbines. When the decision-maker is risk-sensitive (VaR at $\alpha = 99\%$), the energy mix changes only under the high-VRE scenario, where dispatchable power generation technologies continue to be prioritized over intermittent sources.

Although solar and wind energy are expected to form the backbone of the climate-neutral German power sector by the mid-century, there is no clear consensus in the literature on the future deployment of VREs, due to the influence of numerous interdependent factors [106]. For instance, projections of future solar PV capacity in Germany range

from 44 GW to 669 GW [61,107]. Similarly, our study shows that VREs, with more than 85% of total power generation capacity in 2050, are dominant clean technologies and the way forward to achieve a carbon-neutral power sector; however, our numbers differ from other sources.

Under the risk-sensitive scenario with $\alpha = 99\%$, the installed capacity for solar PV is expected to reach 153 GW at the end of the planning horizon under both low-and high-VRE scenarios, which is higher than 120 GW (including rooftop) under region network scenario, but lower than 275 GW of constrained potential, as calculated in Klaus et al. [108]. Our solar PV calculation is also lower than the latest German

Fig. 8. Capacity mix of the power system in 2050 under Low- and High-VRE for the risk-neutral and the risk-averse cases (i.e., VaR at $\alpha = 99\%$).

Fig. 9. Capacity development of VRE until 2050 with markers to show the German targets for installed and announced capacities as stated in the German NECP.

climate legislation, which sets a goal of 215 GW by 2030 [34] and 385 GW in 2045 proposed by Prognos et al. [107].

For offshore wind energy, the deployed capacity ranges from 49.2 GW to 57 GW, while onshore wind capacity spans from 87.5 GW to 90.5 GW. Germany has set targets to increase offshore and onshore wind capacities to 70 GW and 145 GW by 2045, respectively [107]. These targets exceed the cost-optimal levels, implying greater reliance on VREs instead of fossil fuels. For better visualization, Fig. 9 shows the capacities and the respective targets until 2050. Please note that these targets are not imposed on the model, allowing the solver to find the cost-optimal solutions. In our model, carbon neutrality can be achieved by purchasing carbon credits from other countries at a price 10% higher

than carbon prices. Hence, the model explores various domestic and international pathways to achieve carbon neutrality in a cost-optimal manner.

The calculated cost-optimal capacities under VaR with $\alpha = 99\%$ require between 3893 and 3974 km² land in Germany, assuming the mean specific space requirements for onshore wind power plants and solar power plants are 0.027 km² per MW [109] and 0.01 km² per MW [110], respectively. Purr et al. [111] presume an available area for ground-mounted PV systems of 3150 km², which is more than twice the area required by 2050 according to our calculations. And in accordance with a recently passed German law, 2% of the country's total land area (7100 km²) is to be allocated for onshore wind energy

by 2032 [35]. However, the available capacity is also influenced by social factors. Tsani et al. [112] demonstrate a declining trend in land availability for solar PV and onshore wind turbines, as populations seek to protect landscapes by keeping renewables out of sight. In the most extreme case, only 44 GW and 3 GW would remain available for open-field PV and onshore wind turbines, respectively. To reduce future land-use conflicts, innovative technologies that co-use land, such as installed PV on parking lots, water bodies (i.e., floating-PV), or agricultural areas (i.e., agri-PV) are viable options, though their potentials are not fully investigated yet [113,114].

In this study, we assume a conservative growth for the future expansion of VREs. However, if we assume higher bullish growth rates for VREs,⁹ the impact of weather variations will be significantly reduced. For example, the demand for bioenergy will be reduced and limited to only extreme cases. The GHG emissions between various settings are almost flattened between 9,240,000 and 9,290,000 KtCO₂-eq since excess deployment of VREs reduces the need for fossil energy. Among VREs, solar energy is the cheapest technology, taking advantage of most opportunities. In the mid-century, solar energy could produce 2.6 times more electricity than wind energy (onshore and offshore). This translates to 384.54 GW solar PVs and 87.17 GW wind onshore, requiring 6199 km² land.

5.3. The impact of climate change on biomass

Until this section, all the plots presented in this manuscript were based on the best possible yields under RCP2.6, as described in Esmaeili Aliabadi et al. [81]. However, climate change could impact the bioenergy supply chain by reducing biomass production. In this section, we investigate how the worst yields under RCP6.0 can shape the cost-optimal solution in comparison with the best yields under RCP2.6.

Fig. 10 depicts the differences between the optimal decision variables for the risk-neutral case and for CVaR with $\alpha = 95\%$, obtained by subtracting the results under RCP2.6 from those under RCP6.0. In both risk-neutral and risk-sensitive cases, the plots can be conceptually divided by an imaginary line, separating the low-VRE corner from the remaining area. In this section, we refer to the area near the low-VRE corner as *Region-A* throughout this section, and the rest as *Region-B*.

According to results, the total system cost of the German energy system is consistently lower under RCP2.6 compared to RCP6.0, as $\sum_t (z_t^{RCP2.6} - z_t^{RCP6.0}) < 0$. However, in Region-A, the cost difference becomes even more pronounced, with significantly higher (i.e., more negative) costs observed under RCP6.0. This is due to a multitude of reasons, such as the combined scarcity of affordable biomass and VREs under RCP6.0. From the third column of Fig. 10, one can see that biomass production for the power sector is always higher under RCP2.6, as climate change has a less adverse impact on yields under RCP2.6 compared to RCP6.0. In Region-A under RCP6.0, the risk-neutral and risk-sensitive decision-makers adhere to less VRE and bioenergy (due to limited biomass), and more fossil energy (which is partially used in the power sector), leading to more expensive solutions.

The comparison of the risk-neutral case and the risk-averse case shows that, also under RCP6.0, in the risk-averse case, more dispatchable bioenergy is used for power production, although at higher costs. Additionally, the risk-averse case leads to a bigger difference in VRE production between RCP2.6 and RCP6.0.

The outcomes underscore the influence of risk-sensitive decision-makers on fossil fuel policies. In the U.S., for instance, Trump's slogan "Drill, Baby, Drill" [115], which promotes increased fossil energy extraction in response to economic pressures, may reflect similar dynamics. Comparable trends are also evident in political movements in Germany advocating for the rollback of renewable energy initiatives

in favor of fossil fuels and nuclear power [116]. In a nutshell, in the pursuit of a clean energy transition with low total system cost, fossil fuels may become the third wheel while VRE and bioenergy engage in a coordinated tango.

6. Conclusions

The reliable power sector is essential for the clean energy transition, especially given the electrification efforts across all sectors. That said, achieving a secure power sector is deemed challenging, as intermittent energy sources can introduce unpredictability into the optimal management of energy resources. To address this intermittency, we have developed a stochastic bioenergy optimization model that uses historical data to account for the variability of solar and wind energy, while incorporating risk sensitivity through value-at-risk and conditional value-at-risk measures. Our formulation enables the execution of large-scale national and international energy system optimization models with risk-sensitivity within a computationally reasonable time. Our results indicate that VREs are the cornerstone of Germany's clean energy system, while bioenergy, as a flexible technology, can help mitigate the variabilities amid extreme weather years with limited VRE availability. It can be noted that the analysis does not yield a single optimal solution applicable under all circumstances. A risk-neutral approach can result in lower total system cost, while excessive risk aversion can undermine emission reduction efforts by persuading decision-makers to invest in more peaker plants that burn natural gas. This impact became more pronounced under the severe climate change scenario (i.e., RCP6.0), where shortages of affordable biomass and VREs trigger a downward spiral, leading to increased fossil fuel consumption and total system cost. Finally, VRE deployment in various German federal states shows sensitivity to the availability of renewable sources: Under low-VRE, states in the middle of Germany demonstrate a lower interest in VREs.

This study opens up several pathways for further exploration. In this research, we focused on the supply side while keeping end-use demand constant. However, the cost of electricity is linked to its availability. Therefore, one can derive demand elasticity and allow demand to change as a function of supply. Yet, projecting future demand is difficult as it depends on individual behavior and political decisions. In addition, BESS is not modeled explicitly in this study, which could contribute to smoothing out short-term variability. To simplify the modeling and reduce the runtime, we assume that purchased power follows a normal distribution and is independent of CFs; nevertheless, generalizing the formulation while maintaining linearity in the model can be advantageous. Finally, carbon capture technology is primarily designated for bioenergy to achieve negative emissions; however, post-combustion carbon capture units can also be added to fossil-burning power plants, reducing their emissions. Moreover, expanding CDR concepts to non-energy sectors would create more pathways for carbon management [117].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sandra Gutjahr: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniela Thrän:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources. **Danial Esmaeili Aliabadi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used GPT-based technologies, such as Grammarly, ChatGPT, Writefull (via Overleaf),

⁹ 22 GW additional capacity per year for solar and 10 GW for wind onshore.

Fig. 10. The difference between RCP2.6 and RCP6.0 for CVaR with $\alpha = 50\%$ (top row) and $\alpha = 95\%$ (lower row). The plot corresponding to fossil energy includes natural gas, lignite, and hard coal for all sectors.

and DeepL, in order to translate and improve the readability of the manuscript. All content was subsequently reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the final version.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Nomenclature

- ARO Adaptive Robust Optimization
- BENOPTex the extended Bioenergy Optimization model
- BECCS Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage
- BESS Battery Energy Storage System
- CF Capacity Factor
- CVaR Conditional Value-at-Risk
- ESMs Energy System Models
- ESOMs Energy System Optimization Models
- ESOM Energy System Optimization Model
- GANs Generative Adversarial Networks
- GHG Greenhouse Gas
- IAM Integrated Assessment Model
- IEA International Energy Agency
- LULUCF Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry

- MV Mean-Variance
- NUTS Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
- PV Photovoltaics
- RCP Representative Concentration Pathways
- REMIX Renewable Energy Mix
- V2G Vehicle-to-Grid
- VaR Value-at-Risk
- VRE Variable Renewable Energy

Appendix B. Probability function

Assuming that historic scenarios in each category are the same, then p^s follows the multinomial distribution of $|T|$ independent trials, from which three categories are picked. However, scenarios within each category are assumed to be distinct (i.e., the capacity factors of any two distinct historic years within each category vary for different time slices). Therefore, we use the following proposition to calculate the joint probabilities.

Proposition 1. *Given the scenario s , the joint probabilities can be calculated as $\prod_c \left(\frac{Pr(S_c)}{|S_c|} \right)^{k_c}$, where k_c is the total number of times in $|T|$ independent trial that a scenario from mutually exclusive category c is selected, and $Pr(S_c)$ is the probability of choosing scenario $S_c \in \{low-VRE, mid-VRE, high-VRE\}$, which is given.*

Proof. To calculate the joint probability, we rely on the Bayesian theory. Since the mixture of $S_c \in \{low-VRE, mid-VRE, high-VRE\}$ are given in each scenario s , one can calculate the joint probability of scenario s as $Pr(s_{2020}, \dots, s_{2050}) = Pr(\cap_t s_t | \cap_t s_t \in S_c) \cdot Pr(\cap_t s_t \in S_c) + Pr(\cap_t s_t | \cap_t s_t \notin S_c) \cdot Pr(\cap_t s_t \notin S_c)$, where s_t is the realized historic scenario at future year t among subset of scenarios S_c . Since categories are mutually exclusive, historic data belongs to one and only one category (i.e., $Pr(S_{c_1} \cap S_{c_2}) = \emptyset, \forall c_1 \neq c_2$), the second term is zero. As the realized scenarios in each year are independent of other years, we can simplify $p^s = \prod_t (Pr(s_t | s_t \in S_c) \cdot Pr(s_t \in S_c))$. The first term can be replaced by $\frac{1}{|S_c|}$ and the second term is defined by s as the portion of times we would like to have category c in $|T|$ independent trials when $|T| \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e., $Pr(S_c)$). The production can be rewritten based on category instead of year as $\prod_c \left(\frac{Pr(S_c)}{|S_c|} \right)^{k_c}$, where $\sum_c k_c = |T|$. \square

Appendix C. Measuring dependency

Proposition 2. $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \approx 0$.

Proof. In principle, \tilde{C}_{tjir} and \tilde{P}_{tjir} have a non-positive correlation (and covariance) for any fixed tuple of (t, j, i, r) , as increasing CFs will reduce the need to purchase expensive power from other channels in region r at time slice j of year t (i.e., $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \leq 0$). However, \tilde{C}_{tjir} is influenced by weather conditions, while the purchased power \tilde{P}_{tjir} is primarily determined by energy sector characteristics—such as electricity demand and the availability of external power purchases (see Eq. (3)). Therefore, the two variables can be reasonably considered independent (or non-linearly dependent as the decision on purchasing power is affected by many sectors and stakeholders), meaning that their covariance is near zero. \square

Assuming that the two random variables are not fully independent, we derive the theoretical bound for the covariance between \tilde{C}_{tjir} and \tilde{P}_{tjir} in Appendix C.1.

C.1. Bound on dependencies

Proposition 3. $-\tilde{C}_{tjir} \times \hat{P}_{tr} \leq cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \leq 0$.

Proof. For a fixed (t, i, j, r) , one can logically infer that a higher capacity factor reduces reliance on purchasing power from more expensive external sources, and vice versa; in other words, $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \leq 0$. We also know by the definition of covariance that $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}\tilde{P}_{tjir}] - \mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]\mathbb{E}[\tilde{P}_{tjir}]$. The minimum covariance happens when the first term is at a minimum (i.e., $\min(\mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}\tilde{P}_{tjir}])$) and the second term is at a maximum (i.e., $\max(\mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]\mathbb{E}[\tilde{P}_{tjir}])$). Since all variables are non-negative (i.e., $\tilde{C}_{tjir} \geq 0$ and $\tilde{P}_{tjir} \geq 0$), the minimum value of the first term is zero. As \tilde{C}_{tjir} is the input to the model, we can compute $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}] = \tilde{C}_{tjir} \geq 0$. Also, from Eq. (3), we know that $\tilde{P}_{tjir} \leq \hat{P}_{tr}$ for all elements; therefore, $\mathbb{E}[\tilde{P}_{tjir}] \leq \hat{P}_{tr}$. Thus, the maximum value for the second term is $\tilde{C}_{tjir} \times \hat{P}_{tr}$. By combining the minimum and maximum of two previous terms, one can infer $\min cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) = 0 - \tilde{C}_{tjir} \times \hat{P}_{tr}$. \square

Corollary 1. $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \approx 0$ when \hat{P}_{tr} is sufficiently small.

Proof. This corollary can be directly proved by calculating $\lim_{\hat{P}_{tr} \rightarrow 0} cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir})$. By the sandwich theorem, the minimum value converges to zero, while the maximum value is zero, meaning $\lim_{\hat{P}_{tr} \rightarrow 0} cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) = 0$. \square

Corollary 2. $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \in (-0.052, 0)$ when $\hat{P}_{tr} = 100$ and $|J| = 730$.

Proof. In this study, $\max \tilde{C}_{tjir} \leq 0.38$, as the capacity factor of offshore wind, which is the most efficient technology, is below 0.38. Assuming that all \hat{P}_{tr} is assigned to offshore wind and in a single region, we can calculate $cov(\tilde{C}_{tjir}, \tilde{P}_{tjir}) \geq -\frac{100}{730} \times 0.38 = 0.052$. \square

Assuming that the utility-scale BESS in Germany is expected to remain below one PJ by 2050 [8], one can assume that the only source of purchase is from prosumers [118], since the direct import of electricity from other countries is governed by π_{tis} . Please note that when the regional VREs are affected, so are the local prosumers; therefore, their power to supply electricity into the grid is a function of their storage and consumption, and the bidirectional grid capacity of connected regions. While various levels of \hat{P}_{tr} are investigated in Appendix G.6, analyzing the availability of purchasable power by prosumers is complex and beyond the scope of this study.

Fig. D.11. Quantile–quantile plot of 48 sample data for \tilde{P}_{tjir} values limited to $j = 2$ and $i = \text{wind onshore}$ in smaller case study.

Appendix D. Normality

To simplify VaR and CVaR, we assume \tilde{P}_{tjir} follows the normal distribution. However, the normality is case dependent and difficult to prove. Using the Shapiro–Wilk test with the significance level of 0.005 over the results of a small case study, in which a representative setting comprising 50% mid-VRE and 25% each of low- and high-VRE, for a NUTS-0 energy system with $|J| = 5$ is solved one hundred times ($K = 100$), we show that \tilde{P}_{tjir} follows the normal distribution ($p\text{-value} = 0.006755$) for certain technologies and time slices. Fig. D.11 shows an example quantile–quantile plot of the data for wind onshore and time slice $j = 2$.

While we assume that \tilde{P}_{tjir} follows a normal distribution, future research could extend the proposed framework to accommodate more general distributional forms. Statistical power transformation techniques, such as Box–Cox and Yeo–Johnson, allow non-normal data to be transformed toward normality. However, in this context, such transformations should be applied to the expression $E_{tjir}^{el} - \beta_j k_{ii} \mathbb{E}[\tilde{C}_{tjir}]$, which impacts the tractability of the model.

Appendix E. Statistical analysis of all results

Across 15 sets of results under varying settings and scenarios (i.e., 225 samples), the analysis indicates that VRE sources remain the central backbone of the German energy system. Investment in solar and wind power can therefore be characterized as a “no-regret” strategy. Nonetheless, ensuring preparedness for extreme low-VRE conditions through the deployment of bioenergy resources can support Germany in maintaining an affordable and reliable electricity supply. Investments in bioenergy systems sufficient to supply 4707.74 PJ over the planning horizon (2020–2050) will ensure the adequacy of the German energy system in more than 95% of modeled cases (see Fig. E.12).

Appendix F. Optimality and feasibility

Assuming that x^* is the optimal solution of the original model and \hat{x} is the optimal solution of the modified model, this section provides evidence that these two solutions are nearly the same.

F.1. Risk-neutral model

Without expectation in the objective function, x^* should satisfy all combinations of weather scenarios, resulting in a sub-optimal and highly conservative solution (i.e., fat solution) [119]. However, in the risk-neutral case, we assume that the decision-maker is interested in the optimal decision variables for the average condition. Thus, the

Fig. E.12. Distribution of total VRE versus bioenergy under all scenarios and settings in this manuscript (i.e., 225 samples). (b) 225 samples are drawn on a logarithmic scale.

purchase cost of the average scenario has to be taken into account. To this end, one way is to solve the model for an innumerable number of scenarios, and for each scenario, preserve the purchased power and assign the probability of occurrence to approximate $\mathbb{E}[\hat{P}_{tjir}]$ in the objective function. For real-world energy system models, this strategy is impractical. Instead, we converted Eq. (4) to compute the average purchased power, reducing the computation time to only one run, while keeping the accuracy of the model.

Considering that the risk-neutral case requires an average condition, the conversion should create the same solution. Otherwise, there is another average with a different x^* from \hat{x} . Then, it means

$$x^* \neq \hat{x} \Rightarrow \mathbb{E}[P_{tjir}^*] \neq \mathbb{E}[\hat{P}_{tjir}]$$

For simplicity, it is assumed that no alternative optimal solution exists. Then, we know from Eq. (8) when the related constraints (Eq. (2)) are active

$$\begin{aligned} E_{tjir}^{el} - \beta_j k_{ri} \mathbb{E}[C_{tjir}^*] &\neq E_{tjir}^{el} - \beta_j k_{ri} \mathbb{E}[\hat{C}_{tjir}] & , \forall i \in I^{VRE}, j \in J, r \in R \\ \mathbb{E}[C_{tjir}^*] &\neq \mathbb{E}[\hat{C}_{tjir}] & , \forall i \in I^{VRE}, j \in J, r \in R \end{aligned}$$

However, this is not possible, as we calculated the average capacity factors over the same sets. The alternative case occurs when Eq. (2) is inactive, meaning that E_{tjir}^{el} is below the full generation capacity of VRE. Therefore, the corresponding purchased power deemed unnecessary $P_{tjir}^* = \hat{P}_{tjir} = 0$, which contradicts the assumption.

F.2. Risk-sensitive model

For the risk-averse case (VaR), Eq. (15) is obtained directly from Eq. (9) under the assumptions of normally distributed \hat{P}_{tjir} and negligible covariance. Accordingly, provided that these assumptions hold, the optimization model using Eq. (15) as the objective function is expected to yield the same solution as the model based on Eq. (9).

Appendix G. The BENOPTex model

In this study, we employed the stochastic version of the extended bioenergy optimization model. While the main text focuses on our contribution—the stochastic components—the deterministic terms were omitted for brevity. In this section, however, we provide a more detailed explanation of the deterministic parts of the objective function and the relevant constraints.

BENOPTex includes many more constraints and variables, most of which have already been documented in previous publications; therefore, interested readers are referred to Sadr et al. [120] for BECCS, Aliabadi et al. [88] for renewable energy directive, Musonda et al. [84] for chemicals, and to Millinger et al. [22] and Jordan et al. [121] for information on generic constraints (e.g., land use availability, residues, capacity expansion, production bound, H₂ and CH₄ production/consumption, capacity ramp-up, required feedstock, demand for other sectors, vehicle expansion, heat sector). The social, economic, and ecological dimensions of carbon dioxide removal concepts in our model are discussed in detail in Wollnik et al. [122].

Fig. G.13 illustrates the BENOPTex system boundary and the conversion pathways from primary energy carriers (crude oil, natural gas, hydropower, geothermal, solar irradiation, and wind) to secondary energy carriers (heat, electricity, and fuels), which supply energy demand across various end-use sectors (heat, power, transport, and chemicals). Each end-use sector is further divided into subsectors. For example, the transport sector includes road passenger, road freight, shipping, aviation, and rail, while the heat sector is disaggregated into 19 subsectors. The dashed lines indicate CO₂ removal through BECCS, with subsequent use in PtX pathways or permanent storage. Additionally, CO₂ can be stored via nature-based solutions such as forest management.

G.1. Objective function

Eq. (G.1) defines the total system cost as an objective function in million Euros (Mil €), where the decision variables are denoted in bold. The stochastic term is denoted by $\tilde{f}(\lambda, \alpha, p_{ii}^{el}, P_{tjir}^s)$, which represents either a risk-neutral or a risk-sensitive function. The deterministic terms (z) are divided into seven categories: production costs, investments in capacities and transmission lines, production cost of domestic feedstock, cost of imported feedstock, penalties for CO₂ emissions, and the purchase of carbon credits from the international market. In addition, we include an additional revenue term (z^5) for CO₂ capture and storage.

$$\min z = \sum_I (z^{(I)}) + \tilde{f}(\lambda, \alpha, p_{ii}^{el}, P_{tjir}^s) \quad (G.1)$$

where:

$$z^{(1)} = \underbrace{\sum_{i,j,s} (m_{ii}^{opex} + \dot{m}_i^{el} p_{ti}^{el} + \dot{m}_i^{th} p_i^{th} + \dot{m}_i^{CO_2} p_i^{CO_2})}_{\text{Production costs}} \times \pi_{tis} \quad (G.2)$$

Fig. G.13. The scheme of reference energy system in BENOPTex.

Fig. G.14. Comparison of required CO₂ credit to compensate for GHG emissions exceeding targets in high-VRE scenario. The upper trends represent actual emissions (in MtCO₂-eq), whereas the lower trends indicate national targets (in MtCO₂-eq). The gap is shaded in red, showing the required external carbon credits.

$$\mathbf{z}^{(2)} = \underbrace{\sum_{t,i} (I_{ti}^+ k_{ti}^{endo})}_{\text{Investment cost}} + \underbrace{\sum_{r_1, r_2} (I_{r_1 r_2}^+ \| r_1 - r_2 \| F_{ir_1 r_2}^+)}_{\text{Transmission line cost}} \quad (\text{G.3})$$

$$\mathbf{z}^{(3)} = \underbrace{\sum_{t,i,f,c,r} (p_{t f c r} m_{i f c r}^{dom})}_{\text{Utilized domestic feedstock cost}} + \underbrace{\sum_{t,i,f,r} (p_{t f r}^{imp} m_{i f r}^{imp})}_{\text{Cost of imported feedstock}} \quad (\text{G.4})$$

$$\mathbf{z}^{(4)} = \underbrace{\sum_{d,t,i,r} (p_t^{CO_2} \epsilon_{ii}^{FF} \delta_{d i i r}^{FF})}_{\text{Penalizing the use of fossil fuels}} + \underbrace{\sum_t (\hat{p}_t^{CO_2} m_t^{CO_2})}_{\text{Carbon credit cost}} \quad (\text{G.5})$$

$$\mathbf{z}^{(5)} = \underbrace{-\sum_{t,i} (p_t^{CO_2} \psi_{ti})}_{\text{Revenue from storing CO}_2} \quad (\text{G.6})$$

For technology i , m_{ti}^{opex} accounts for its marginal cost at time t , (including labor and other inputs, excluding feedstock inputs, and minus revenue from selling byproducts). The energy consumed in the technology as heat or electricity is represented by m_i^{th} and m_i^{el} in $\frac{MWh}{PJ}$ multiplied by its correspondent cost p_{ii}^{el} and p_i^{th} in $\frac{\text{Mil } \text{€}}{MWh}$. π_{tis} is the production of output in PJ from technology i at time t for market (sector) s .

Endogenously net installed capacity (minus decommissioned capacity) at time t for technology i showed by k_{ti}^{endo} in GW while the levelized investment cost showed by I_{ti}^+ in $\frac{\text{Mil } \text{€}}{GW}$. $I_{r_1 r_2}^+$ denotes the unit investment cost of a high-voltage transmission line per kilometer and per PJ, which is multiplied by the Euclidean distance between regions r_1 and r_2 . $F_{ir_1 r_2}^+$ represents the additional transmission capacity (in PJ) established between the two regions in year t by the model, which is different from already planned transmission lines (i.e., $\hat{F}_{ir_2 r_2}$).

$p_{t f c r}$ represents the price at time t for feedstock f in category c (three categories) for the region r in $\frac{\text{Mil } \text{€}}{PJ}$ and $m_{i f c r}$ describes the feed used in PJ. The imported cost comprises $m_{i f r}^{imp}$, which is the price of imported feedstock in PJ multiplied by its price $p_{t f r}^{imp}$ in $\frac{\text{Mil } \text{€}}{PJ}$ for feedstock f consumed in technology i in region r at time t . z_4 punishes those technologies that combust fossil fuels and emit CO₂ into the atmosphere. When the optimal solution emits more than the GHG targets, the model purchases carbon credit from external partners with higher price than carbon price ($\hat{p}_t^{CO_2} \geq p_t^{CO_2}$) to compensate for the overshoot. Lastly, in $z^{(5)}$, the revenue from storing CO₂ calculated based on the amount of CO₂ sequestered and stored by technology i and the carbon price $p_t^{CO_2}$ over time in $\frac{\text{€}}{tCO_2}$.

Fig. G.15. Cost versus VRE risk under various settings.

$$F_{t,r_1,r_2} + F_{t,r_2,r_1} \leq \hat{F}_{t,r_1,r_2} + F_{t,r_1,r_2}^+, \quad \forall t \in T, r_1, r_2 \in R \quad (\text{G.7})$$

$$\dot{m}_{tjr}^{el} \leq (\pi_{tjr}^{el} - \delta_{tjr}^{el}) + \frac{\sum_{r_2} \left((0.97^{\|r-r_2\|} F_{t,r_2,r} - F_{t,r,r_2} \right)}{j^{max}} + \pi_{tjr}^{el-imp}, \quad \forall t \in T, j \in J, r, r_2 \in R \quad (\text{G.8})$$

G.2. Regional electricity demand and transmission network

The data related to the transmission network is taken from the GENeSYS-MOD model [123]. The flow of electricity between regions should not exceed the capacity of the transmission lines. The flow of electricity between regions is governed via Eqs. (G.7) and (G.8). Eq. (G.7) sets a cap ($\hat{F}_{t,r_1,r_2} + F_{t,r_1,r_2}^+$) for electricity flow between two regions r_1 and r_2 . The planned transmission lines (\hat{F}_{t,r_1,r_2}) are distinguished from those determined by the model (F_{t,r_1,r_2}^+), since the planned lines do not incur additional costs for the system.

In Eq. (G.8), electricity used at time slice j of year t in region r (i.e., \dot{m}_{tjr}^{el}) should be less than the domestic excess production of electricity in region r (i.e., $\pi_{tjr}^{el} - \delta_{tjr}^{el}$), net electricity dispatched from other regions to region r and imported electricity to region r (i.e., π_{tjr}^{el-imp}) combined, considering the loss in the network (0.97% in each 1000 km). j^{max} is the total number of times slices.

The projection of regional electricity demand and hourly pattern is adopted from the Renewable Energy Mix (REMIX) model [89]. In Eq. (G.9), power produced from all sources (e.g., VRE, fossil, bioenergy) satisfies the exogenous yearly end-use demand (δ_{st}) and the endogenous demand, which is used (for instance) by battery electric vehicles and electrolyzers. Also, Eq. (G.10) ensures that the capacity of the consuming demand technology is sufficient to utilize the requested power. η_{ti} denotes the energetic conversion efficiency of feed (power here) to main energy carrier (e.g., H_2).

$$\delta_{st} + \sum_{r,j,i \in I^{el-in}} \dot{m}_{tjir}^{el} = \sum_{i \in I^{el-out}} \pi_{tis}, \quad \forall t \in T, s = \{\text{power market}\} \quad (\text{G.9})$$

$$\eta_{ti} \dot{m}_{tjir}^{el} \leq \beta_j k_{ij} C_{tir}, \quad \forall t \in T, j \in J, i \in I^{el-in} \quad (\text{G.10})$$

G.3. Available land for bioenergy

In BENOPTex, the yield values from RCP scenarios (\hat{y}_{tjfr}) are translated to the land demand for energy crops — considering their energy density and dried matter content as described in Millinger et al. [22] and used as a parameter in Eq. (G.11):

$$\sum_{i,f,c} (Y_{tjfr} \dot{m}_{tifcr}) \leq \Lambda_{tr} \quad \forall t \in T, r \in R \quad (\text{G.11})$$

where Λ_{tr} is the available land for energy crops in each region at year t and \dot{m}_{tifcr} is a decision variable representing feed f used in region r from category c by technology i at year t in petajoules (PJ). Eq. (G.11) restricts the expected production of energy crops from different regions. To comply with the National Biomass Strategy (NABIS) in Germany [124], we assume that the current land area used for bioenergy in Germany (approximately 24,000 km^2) serves as the maximum limit, which gradually decreases by 10% toward mid-century.

G.4. Accounting emissions

BENOPTex is required to comply with Germany's legally mandated annual sectoral emission budgets \bar{B}_t , presented in Table G.2, which are implemented as a binding constraint, as specified in Eq. (G.13). $B_t^{CO_2}$ calculates the annual GHG emissions within the system boundary via Eq. (G.12). In this equation, ψ_{ti}^{BECCS} and ψ_{tir}^{NS} specify the amount of sequestered CO_2 by BECCS and natural sinks, respectively.

Fig. G.16. The German energy system under a risk-neutral case ($\lambda = 1$ and $\alpha = 50\%$) and different $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr}$ values in each row. The first column displays the cost, while the second and third columns show the produced energy through the planning horizon by VRE and bioenergy, respectively. Each point is replicated 10,000 times with the temporal resolution of 730 time slices per year.

According to Eq. (G.13), ϵ_t^{AG} represents emissions originating from exogenous non-energy sectors (such as agriculture).¹⁰ The variable $m_t^{CO_2}$ denotes the quantity of purchased CO₂ credits from outside Germany to offset emissions that exceed the stipulated targets. Eq. (G.13) divides $B_t^{CO_2}$ and $m_t^{CO_2}$ by 1000 to convert units from kilotonnes to million tonne. Fig. G.14 depicts the gap between the emissions corresponding to the optimal solution and the determined targets in each year using a red area ($m_t^{CO_2}$). The larger the shaded area, the greater the reliance on external countries for the provision of credits.

CO₂ credit price plays an important role in the economic viability of BECCS technologies. The higher the CO₂ credit price, the higher the

contribution of domestic BECCS concepts in CO₂ removal. We assume that the carbon credit price $\hat{p}_t^{CO_2}$ is slightly higher (10% more expensive under the base scenario) than the domestic carbon price ($p_t^{CO_2}$) in the same year; therefore, our model tries to reach climate targets using domestic resources. Interested readers are referred to Sadr et al. [120], in which a more extensive sensitivity analysis with respect to various parameters is conducted over the deterministic BENOPTex model.

$$\sum_{d,t} (\epsilon_{dt}^{FF} \times \delta_{dt}^{FF}) - \sum_t (\epsilon_{it}^- \times \pi_{its}^{ch}) - \sum_t \psi_{it}^{BECCS} - \sum_{i,r} \psi_{tir}^{NS} = B_t^{CO_2} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \tag{G.12}$$

$$\frac{B_t^{CO_2}}{1000} + \epsilon_t^{AG} - \frac{m_t^{CO_2}}{1000} \leq \bar{B}_t \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \tag{G.13}$$

¹⁰ It was implemented via an external parameter, which is calculated based on published targets [33].

Table G.2

Permissible annual emission amounts for the years 2020–2050 (according to German national climate law [33]).

Sector	2020	2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
All Sectors	900 ^a	643	438	292	150	0	−50 ^b
Agriculture	70	60.1	56.6	50.8	45	40.25	35.5

^a The 2020 value is adjusted upward to avoid distortions from the COVID-19-induced emission drop.

^b The projected negative value for 2050 is based on a conservative extrapolation, as Germany has not yet specified a precise target and has only indicated an intention to achieve net-negative emissions beyond 2045.

G.5. Analysis of risk-cost

Fig. G.15 illustrates how different risk measures reduce variability at the expense of increased total system cost. The total system cost for all settings is shown on the y-axis, while variability is exhibited as the difference between the lower value (i.e., High-VRE: 100%) and the upper value (i.e., Low-VRE: 100%) under each risk measure. The largest cost increase occurs when moving from the risk-neutral case, equivalent to a VaR with $\alpha = 50\%$, to a more risk-averse setting with VaR at $\alpha = 95\%$. As decision-makers become more risk-sensitive, the slope of all trends decreases. The point at which further cost increases are no longer justified by the associated reduction in risk depends on the decision-maker's preferences.

G.6. Analysis of maximum purchased electricity

Fig. G.16 depicts the ternary graph of the risk-neutral German energy system (i.e., $\alpha = 50\%$) under various scenario settings with the resolution of 25% and maximum purchasable power values (i.e., $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr} \in \{10, 70, 100, 200\}$). The maximum cost difference (approximately 10%) across all triangular plots in this manuscript is observed when $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr} = 10$, which drops to 5% when $\sum_r \hat{P}_{tr} = 70$. This implies that the unavailability of purchasable electricity to compensate for low-VRE scenarios forces the model to resort to more expensive options. Allowing the model to procure higher volumes of power aids in eliminating more expensive generation options by relaxing constraint (3). Thus, increasing \hat{P}_{tr} enables the model to soften the cost difference between the worst setting (the left wing of the triangle) and the best setting (the head of the triangle). This outcome is also in accordance with Gutjahr et al. [125], in which the extreme events were studied.

Data availability

The generated results and plotter for this study can be found in <https://git.ufz.de/esmaeil/sto-benoptex.git>.

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